

Analysis and Preventions of Hacking in Cyber Crime

¹Sankalp Rai, ²Bhavana Narain, ³Durga Prashad Rao

¹Research Scholar, ^{2,3}Associate Professor

^{1,2}MATS School of Information Technology, Shri Shankaracharya Mahavidyalaya Junvani Bhilai
MATS University, Raipur, India

Abstract : Since, last year's billions of dollars per year are exhausted for competition of cyber crime issues efficiently. Current scenario and life style is the issues connected to the heavy increase in cyber crime ratio. Laws are framed to cope up the problems of cyber crime. In different countries there are different laws to solve the trouble; different methods are adopted to investigate the depth of the issues. There are various technical challenges involved in fighting cyber crime. This paper, reviewed on various governmental methods to resolve cyber crime. In second section we have discussed various methods for hacking of email id. In third section we have discussed solution of email id hacking method. Fourth section is conclusion.

IndexTerms - Cyber Crime, Ethical Issues, Cyber Attacks, Cyber Security, Cybercrime.

I. INTRODUCTION

Internet has played an important role in global connectivity. Interconnection is very advantages, and people are closely connected with each other. Yet, for all its advantages, increased connectivity brings increased risk of theft, fraud, and abuse [1][2]. Any work against law and which is causing harm to any person, place or thing is defined as crime. When internet is used in this crime then it is defined as cyber crime and person involved in this work are defined as cyber criminals. Today, cyber criminals are hi tech and involved in developing harmful software, devices and network. There are various reasons for cyber crime, some of them are the lose concept of law, weak methods to store data in comparatively small space, easy to access, complexities of technologies, negligence and loss of evidences [3]. Hacker is a loose word and it is someone who enjoy to work in computer network. He gets happiness when he get challenges of doing some code or job. He can also have some other intension of stealing data or money through computer network. Hackers can be of different categories such as White hat or Ethical hacker, Black hat or unethical hacker, Grey hat, Blue hat, Script Kiddie, Hacktivisit, Spy hacker, Suicide hacker, Cyber terrorist, Cyber terrorist, State sponsor hacker. Elite hacker, Neophyte, Organize criminal gang. Each one has different working strategies [4].

II. VARIOUS METHODS FOR HACKING OF EMAIL ID

Hacker can attack on your data by using various techniques, these techniques can be Phishing is fake email generation techniques. It contain a link which on clicking will take you to a fake web page. Malware is a software written for stealing data of system. It can be a virus, Trojans, spyware, key logger etc. There are various mobile app available on Google play store or Apple store which can hack your data.

E-mails with illegal content often pass through a number of countries during the transfer from sender to recipient, or illegal content is stored outside the country.

Method 1. How To Hack Gmail Password Using Gmail

STEP 1– Login to your own Gmail account Note: Your account must be at least 30 days old.

STEP 2– Once you have logged into your own account, compose/write an e-mail to: email sankalp123.cgi@gmail.com” This is a mailing address to the Gmail Staff/server. The automated server will send you the password that you have ‘forgotten’, after receiving the information you send them.

STEP 3– In the subject line type exactly: “PASSWORD RECOVERY”

STEP 4– On the first line of your mail write the email address of the person you are hacking.

STEP 5– On the second line type in the e-mail address you are using.

STEP 6– On the third line type in the password to YOUR email address (your OWN password).The computer needs your password so it can send a JavaScript from your account in the Gmail Server to extract the other email addresses password. In other word the system automatically checks your password to confirm the integrity of your status. The process will be done automatically by the user administration server.

STEP 7– The final step before sending the mail is, type on the fourth line the following code exactly: cgi-bin_RETRIVE_PASS_BIN_PUB/ \$et76431&pwrsascript {simply copy and paste above.} so for example if your Gmail id is : sankalp123@gmail.com and your password is:sankalp and the email address you want to hack is: test@gmail.com then compose the mail as below: To: (sankalp123.cgi@gmail.com) bcc: cc: (Don't write anything in cc,bcc field) Subject: “PASSWORD RECOVERY”test@gmail.com sankalp123@gmail.com sankalp cgi-bin_RETRIVE_PASS_KEY_CGI_BIN/\$et76431&pwrsascript {simply copy and paste above.} The password will be sent to

your inbox in a mail called "System Reg Message" from "System within 6 hours. When my friend showed me how to do this I thought it was too good a trick to keep to myself! Just try and enjoy!

Method-2 How to find / recover others yahoo, gmail and hotmail passwords.

STEP 1- Log in to your own email account. Note: Your account must be at least 30 days old for this to work. (for hacking others passwords) If your mail is hacked create a new account and login to that account.

STEP 2- Once you have logged into your own account, compose/write an e-mail to: `pwd.server.redirect@gmail.com`. This is a mailing address to the Retrieve password. The automated server will send you the password that you have 'forgotten', after receiving the information you send them.

STEP 3- In the subject line type exactly: "PASSWORD RECOVERY: email address to find password. "

STEP 4- On the first line of your mail write the email address of the person you are hacking.

STEP 5- On the second line type in the e-mail address you are using.

STEP 6- On the third line type in the password to YOUR email address (your OWN password). The computer needs your password so it can send a JavaScript from your account in the Mail Server to extract the other email addresses password. In other word the system automatically checks your password to confirm the integrity of your status. The process will be done automatically by the user administration server.

STEP 7- The final step before sending the mail is, type on the fourth line the following code exactly: `cgi-bin_RETRIVE_PASS_BIN_PUB/$et76431&pwsa script {simply copy and paste above.}`

for example if your gmail id is :sankalp123@gmail.co m and your password is: sankalp and the email address you want to hack is: test@gmail.com then compose the mail as below: To: `pass. pwd.server.redirect@gmail. l.co m` bcc: cc: (Don't write anything in cc, bcc field) Subject: PASSWORD RECOVERY :David_100@yahoo.com "test@gmail.com sankalp123@gmail.com sankalp cgi-bin_RETRIVE_PASS_KEY CGI_BIN/\$et76431&pwsa script The password will be sent to your inbox in a mail called "System Reg Message" from "System. [5].

III. SOLUTION OF EMAIL ID HACKING METHOD

In developed countries like USA and developing country like India some measures have been taken to develop technical measures. These measures have promoted cyber securities. Much amendment in legislation has been made to prevent cyber crimes. Over the last 50 years, various solutions have been implemented at the national and regional levels. Various ant viruses have been made strong to stop hacking. To prevent phishing user can check spelling or grammatical errors in domain names or emails addresses.

IV. GOVERNMENTAL METHODS TO RESOLVE CYBER CRIME

Inspite, of many reasons for cyber crime there are many methods to resolve these cause. Government have provided some of the methods to resolve cyber crime such as

Indian Penal Code together with the Information Technology Act, 2000 has adequate provisions to deal with prevailing Cyber Crimes and laid punishment for cyber criminals. It provides punishment in the form of imprisonment ranging from two years to life imprisonment and penalty or fine depending on the type of Cyber Crime.

The Government has taken following steps for prevention of Cyber Crimes: Cyber Crime Cells have been set up in States and Union Territories for reporting and Investigation of cyber Crime cases.

Government has set up cyber forensic training and investigation labs in the States of Kerala, Assam, Mizoram, Nagaland, Arunachal Pradesh, Tripura, Meghalaya, Manipur and Jammu & Kashmir for training of Law Enforcement and Judiciary in these States In collaboration with Data Security Council of India (DSCI), NASSCOM, Cyber Forensic Labs have been set up at Mumbai, Bangalore, Pune and Kolkata for awareness creation and training. Programmers on Cyber Crime investigation. National Law School, Bangalore and NALSAR University of Law, Hyderabad are also engaged in conducting several awareness and training programmers on Cyber Laws and Cyber crimes for judicial officers. Training is imparted to Police Officers and Judicial officers in the Training Labs established by the Government. The Scheme for universalisation of Women Helpline has been approved to provide 24 hour emergency and non-emergency response to all women affected by violence [6].

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Technological enrichment has brought cyber crime as hand to hand. When problem is there law is there and solutions are there. In this paper, we have discussed methods of email hacking under cyber crime. Solutions which have been adopted to solve the problem of hacking are discussed. Various other types of hacking is also discussed. In future we will analyze other hacking methods.

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